

Rapid determination of torsemide in pharmaceuticals and human milk using a new spectrophotometric method

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Abstract : A simple, precise and accurate method for the determination of torsemide in pharmaceutical formulations and human milk. The method is based on oxidation of brucine to bruciquinone in presence of sodium meta periodate and drug produces violet colored complex measured at 550 nm against reagent blank. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 2–14 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ with limit of detection 0.072 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The mean percentage recovery was found to be 99.99. The developed method was successfully applied to the determination of torsemide in pharmaceutical formulations and human milk. No interference was observed in the presence of common pharmaceutical excipients. The developed method does not require extraction.

Keywords : Torsemide, formulation, milk, brucine, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

Torsemide^{1,2} chemically 3-[4-(3-methylphenyl)amino]pyridine-3-yl]sulfonyl-1-propan-2-yl urea (Fig. 1), is a loop diuretic mainly used in the management of edema associated with congestive heart failure. It is also used at low doses for the management of hypertension^{3,4}.

Fig. 1. Structure of torsemide.

Torsemide acts by inhibiting the $\text{Na}^+/\text{K}^+/\text{2Cl}^-$ carrier system⁵ in the lumen of the thick ascending portion of the loop of Henle, resulting in the decrease in reabsorption of sodium and chloride⁶⁻⁹. Literature survey revealed several analytical methods for the determination of diuretics in formulation, which employ techniques such as High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) in human plasma and urine¹⁰ and few spectroscopic methods¹¹ for estimation in formulation. Reported methods involve

complicated time consuming multi step liquid-liquid extraction techniques. Hence simple and precious visible spectrophotometric method was developed for the determination of torsemide in pharmaceutical formulations and human milk.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A Shimadzu UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer (model 2450) with 1 cm matched quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements.

Reagents :

All the chemicals brucine, sodium meta periodate, H_2SO_4 , methanol (SD Fine Chemicals Ltd., Mumbai) used were of analytical reagent grade, double distilled water was used for the preparation of reagents and samples. Torsemide bulk drug was obtained as gift sample from Zydus Lab, Maharashtra, India. Pharmaceutical formulations of torsemide were obtained commercially.

Procedure :

Aliquots of sample solution 2–14 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks. To this solution brucine (3 ml), sodium meta periodate (1.5 ml) and 1.2 M

sulphuric acid (2 ml) were added to each, and the total volume brought to 10 ml with distilled water. The tubes were taken thoroughly and placed in a boiling water bath for about 30 min. The reaction mixture in each tube was cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 25 ml calibrated flask and diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the violet colored complex was measured at 550 nm against a reagent blank, and the amount of the compound was calculated from calibration graph shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Calibration plot.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics :

The absorption spectra of the reaction of oxidized brucine - NaIO_4 with torsemide show absorption maximum at 550 nm against a reagent blank. The functional group such as aliphatic primary amine present in torsemide was exploited for developing the proposed method. The nature of the color species formed in each one has been explained basing on the analogy and probability. The dimethoxy benzene nucleus of brucine is attacked by IO_4^- with the formation of *o*-quinone (bruciquinone) which in turn undergoes nucleophilic attack on the most electron rich proton of coupler (aliphatic primary amine) to give 1-monosubstituted brucinequinone derivative.

Effect of reagent concentration :

To establish the optimum reagent concentrations for complete color development in a total volume of 10 ml, the concentrations of brucine and IO_4^- were varied. The optimum conditions were found to be 1.5–2.5 ml of 0.005 M brucine and 1.2–1.8 ml of 0.005 M IO_4^- .

Effect of acid strength :

The optimum sulphuric acid strength of the 25 ml of diluted reaction mixture for maximum color development with maximum blank color was 0.1–0.15 M.

Detection and quantification limits :

The calculated LOD and LOQ values confirmed that method was sufficiently sensitive. The LOQ was determined by taking the ratio of the SD of the blank with respect to water and the slope of the calibration curve multiplied by the factor 10. This means that LOQ is approximately 4 times greater than LOD. LOD is well below the lower limit of the Beer's law range. Values are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Optical characteristics of proposed methods

Parameters	Values
λ_{max} (nm)	550
Beer's law limit ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	2–14
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	2.35×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001 \text{ A.U}$)	0.0014
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9964
Regression equation (a_A) :	
Slope (b)	0.0652
Intercept (a)	0.0014
% Relative standard deviation ^b	0.243
Color	Violet
LOD ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.072
LOQ ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	0.242
<i>t</i> -test (Theoretical value – 2.306)	0.346
<i>F</i> -test (Theoretical value – 6.39)	3.10
$a_A = a + bc$, where c is the concentration of measured solution in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.	
^b Values in parentheses are the theoretical values for <i>t</i> - and <i>F</i> -values at 95% confidence limits and five degrees of freedom, b_A = average of six determinations.	

Accuracy and precision studies :

The validity of the methods for the assay of torsemide was examined by determining precision and accuracy. These were analyzing six replicates of the drug with in the Beer's law limits. The low values of relative standard deviation (RSD) indicate good precision of the method. The results of analysis of dosage forms are given in Table 2. The results were reproducible as evident from low RSD values.

Table 2. Evaluation of intra-day and inter-day accuracy and precision

Method	Torsemide taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Intra-day			Inter-day		
		Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Recovery \pm RSD%	RE%	Found ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Recovery \pm RSD%	RE%
Brucine	1.0	0.999	99.9 \pm 0.274	-0.1	0.998	99.84 \pm 0.230	-0.160
	3.0	2.999	99.99 \pm 0.086	-0.0067	2.999	99.99 \pm 0.086	-0.006

Interference studies :

The effect of the excipients associated with formulation of torsemide drug in its pure form and its formulation were investigated using the developed method. This method does not suffer any interference from commonly associated excipients and additives in the preparation of tablets such as sucrose, lactose, dextrose, starch, talc and sodium alginate.

Applications :**Assay of pharmaceutical tablets :**

Twenty tablets were weighed and ground to a fine powder using a pestle and a mortar. The average weight of a tablet was calculated. An accurately weighed portion of the powder, equivalent to 100 mg of torsemide was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made up to the mark with water, shaken well and filtered through an Whatman No. 41 filter paper. The concentration of the resulting solution was found to be 1 mg/ml. This solution was considered as the stock. Convenient aliquots from this solution were taken for the determination of torsemide by developed method and results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Determination of torsemide in pharmaceutical dosage forms

Method	Formulation	Taken ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Found ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Recovery \pm RSD
Brucine	Henletor-10	0.5	0.500	100.08 \pm 0.389
		1.0	0.999	98.90 \pm 0.245
	Dytor 200 mg	1.0	0.999	99.94 \pm 0.207
		1.5	1.499	99.94 \pm 0.109

Assay milk samples :

From diuretic mothers milk samples were collected. The samples (10.0 ml) are centrifuged at 3000 r min⁻¹ for 10 min. The solution is filtered and preserved without light at 4 °C. To this various concentration torsemide

samples were analyzed with the developed method, the results are given in Table 4. High accuracy and good recoveries were obtained, which indicates that the developed method can be successfully applied to recover torsemide in milk samples.

Table 4. Method accuracy from recovery assay for the studied analyte

Sample	Added ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Spectrophotometry	
		Found ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Recovery \pm SD
		Milk (10%)	
1	2.0	1.9976	99.88 \pm 0.125
2	4.0	3.9966	99.91 \pm 0.115
3	6.0	5.9898	99.83 \pm 0.241

Conclusions

The proposed method was quite simple and do not require any pretreatment of the drug and tedious extraction procedure. The method has wider linear range with good accuracy and precision. Hence, the data presented in the manuscript by spectrophotometric method for the determination of torsemide in pharmaceutical formulation and human milk demonstrate that the developed method was accurate, precise, linear, selective and offer advantages of reagent availability and stability, less time consumption and high sensitivity. Moreover the method was free from interferences by common additives and excipients.

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